

CITIZENS DIS-ALIGNMENT WITH GOVERNMENT POLICIES: PANACEA TO NIGERIA UNDERDEVELOPMENT

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Abstract

This study visited the underdevelopment problems in Nigeria by examining citizens dis-alignment with government policies. Dis-alignment is when the citizens are unsatisfied with the system thereby separating themselves from government activities and plans, which is largely due to lack of trust and suspicion. The study adopted the systems theory which emphasize understanding and interconnectedness of the components parts within a system, while recognizing the whole, which is greater than the parts. Thus, citizens dis-alignment stem from the fact that Nigeria's underdevelopment is poor leadership governance which, has resulted in her weak economy, poor policy implementation, dilapidated infrastructural facilities, poor health service delivery and low-quality education etc. However, different researches on Nigeria's underdevelopment have argued that bad leadership is not the only obstacle to Nigeria's development, and that Nigeria's citizens have in one way or the other, also contributed to the country's underdevelopment. Relying on secondary data, the study embarked on extensive and in-depth review of relevant literatures on Nigeria's underdevelopment. The study concludes that citizens should align with the country's developmental process as proposed by the government; citizens should hold the leaders accountable for their stewardship in the aspect of policy making and implementation; and that citizens should endeavour to participate in policy making, both at the proposal state to the output stages to aid even development.

Keywords: Citizens dis-alignment, Government policies, Underdevelopment, Leadership

Introduction

Despite Nigeria's abundant natural and human resources, it still struggles to achieve significant progress in providing a decent standard of living for its population, even after many years of independence. Similar to numerous developing nations in Africa, Nigeria grapples with numerous obstacles in its efforts to advance. The nation is plagued by issues such as inequality, poverty, underdevelopment which has deprived many Nigerians of the privileges associated with citizenship (Okon & Thompson, 2020). Citizens typically believed that Nigeria has not recorded any significant or essential transformation since independence. As noted by (Eneh, 2021), by the mid-1990s, Nigeria has been surpassed in development by several nations that were in poorer condition. As a result, Nigeria still ranks among the underdeveloped nations, marked by a fragile industrial sector, low per capital income, elevated levels of illiteracy, poverty, disparity, and diminished life expectancy, among other factors.

Discrepancies in perspectives regarding development and underdevelopment issues in Nigeria are not a recent phenomenon. Some researchers attribute Nigeria's developmental hurdles to the capitalist global economic structure. Conversely, others prefer to introspect in their analysis of Nigeria's underdevelopment predicament. In these context, considerable emphasis was placed on governance. For instance, Achebe (2013) pointed out that Nigeria's issues stem fundamentally from a failure in leadership. Additionally, Rufai (2019) suggested that the best way to understand Nigeria is through the lens of its leadership. He asserted that "since Nigeria's Independence, the lack of competent leaders has been a consistent theme.

Okon & Thompson (2020) contended that "Nigeria's developmental challenges are largely self-inflicted and sustained by the nation's political elite, often characterized as exceedingly self-serving, corrupt, and ineffective". While the short comings of Nigerian leaders have been a focal point of criticism regarding the nation's plight, the responsibility of citizens in the context of Nigeria's unsuccessful development has seldom been addressed. This study aims to contribute by highlighting that, government of Nigeria should sample citizen's consent in policy making in order to share accountability for the

nation's underdevelopment, and this does not contradict any research that implicated Nigerian leaders or pose negative impact on her citizens.

Objectives of the Study

The objectives for this study are: i) to examine if citizens dis-alignment with government policies is a panacea to underdevelopment; ii) to determine if government policies create obstacle to underdevelopment; and iii) to ascertain how policy inconsistency affect development in Nigeria.

Significance of the Study

Study of this nature has significant impact on both variables' government and citizens. The study would be of great benefit to the government on meeting the demands of the citizens and impact the public with trust. This is because lack of trust comes with severe consequences. Nigerian citizens would become adamant in meeting some government demands when there is citizens dis-alignment in government policies. The public trust in government can be evaluated by the extent to which citizens have confidence in the government to operate in the best interests of society. Moreso no government can enjoy absolute trust of its citizens if the power of any government represents a threat to individual freedom and welfare.

Notwithstanding, citizens possess some level of trust for the government, trust is fundamentally important for a healthy and functioning democracy. According to Oaikhena (2023) he posits that "a change in strategy, such as pattern and vision, might not be effective if strategic positions, programmes, products, and attitude do not change accordingly". As a result, citizen compliance with public policies, encourages political participation, and contributes to perceptions of governmental legitimacy.

Stakeholders on the other hand would benefit from this study particularly when they are involved in policy making. The said stakeholders are non-governmental organization (NGOs) who on the other hand, can mediate between the government and the citizens, this will emphatically be a possible panacea for Nigeria underdevelopment and poor policies in the governance.

Concept of Citizenship in Nigeria

As articulated by (Tilly, 2006), citizenship represents an ongoing series of exchange between individuals and representative of a specific state, where each party possesses enforceable right and duties solely due to the individual's membership in group, encompassing both the native born and naturalized, and the representative's affiliation with the state rather than any other authority they may hold. In the view of (Baubock 2002) "citizenship is defined as a status of complete and equally belonging within a self-government political entity, involving rights and responsibilities anchored by particular virtues; thereby implying that citizenship connotes nationality and official association with states".

Based on the aforementioned definitions, a citizen is thus classified as an individual who has officially acquired or been granted the status of full and equal belonging to a state or political community. Citizenship embodies an agreement between the state and its citizens for a reciprocal dynamic (Adejumobi, 2001). While the state provides privileges and rights to its citizens, those citizens owe the state certain obligations and commitments. Notably, the execution of this mutual agreement between the state and citizens does not imply class distinctions but rather civic equality, equal access and opportunities within state institutions frameworks as well as fairness and justice in the relationships among the state individuals and within the political community (Adejumobi, 2001).

In Nigeria, the constitution confers citizenship on every Nigerian, on equal basis. Accordingly, Nigeria's citizenship can be acquired by birth, registration and naturalization. Chapter 3 (Section 25) of the 1999, Constitution states that the following persons are citizens of Nigeria by birth, namely:

- a) Any person born in Nigeria before the date of independence, either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents belong or belonged to a community indigenous to Nigeria;
- b) Every person born in Nigeria after the date of independence either of whose parents or any of whose grandparents is a citizen of Nigeria;
- c) Every person born outside Nigeria either of whose parents is a citizen of Nigeria.

The constitution in section 26 (1-2) also states that a person may be registered as a citizen of Nigeria, if the president is satisfied that: a) He is a person of good character; b) He has shown clear intention of his desire to be domiciled in Nigeria; and c) He has taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed in the Seventh Schedule to the constitution. The provisions of this section also apply to: i) Any woman who is or has been married to a citizen of Nigeria; or b) Every person of full age and capacity born outside Nigeria any of whose grandparents is a citizen of Nigeria.

Furthermore, any person who is qualified in accordance with the provisions of section 27 of the constitution may apply to the president for citizenship by naturalization. The provisions hold that an applicant must prove that:

- a) He is a person of full age and capacity;
- b) He is a person of good character;
- c) He has shown a clear intention of his desire to be domiciled in Nigeria;
- d) He is, in the opinion of Governor of the State where he is or he proposes to be resident, acceptable to the local community in which he is to live permanently, and has been assimilated into the way of life of Nigerians in that part of the Federation;
- e) He is a person who has made or is capable of making useful contribution to the advancement; progress and well-being of Nigeria;
- f) He has taken the Oath of Allegiance prescribed in the Seventh Schedule to the constitution; and
- g) He has, immediately preceding the date of his application, either –
 - Resided in Nigeria for a continuous period of fifteen years; or
 - Resided in Nigeria continuously for a period of twelve months, and during the period of twenty years immediately preceding that period of twelve months has resided in Nigeria for periods amounting in the aggregate to not less than fifteen years.

The aforementioned definition of citizenship in chapter three, along with the fundamental rights outlined in chapter four of the 1999 constitution, which encompasses the right to life, respect for human dignity, personal liberty, equitable hearing, freedom of movement and protection from discrimination, aims to foster national political goals of creating a unified and liberated society for all Nigerians and to enhance mutual responsibilities between the state and its citizens (CFCR, 2002). Nonetheless, the practical application of citizenship in Nigeria has encounter various challenges, it can be perceived as nominal, as citizens largely experience the denial of their citizenship rights, this situation has led individual to adopt subnational identities as a primary source of allegiance and authentic identification (Afolabi, 2016).

Concept of Underdevelopment

Underdevelopment is a complex phenomenon; therefore, it is necessary to clarify the nature of this issue alongside its antonym development. Underdevelopment is simply put, a country that is not developed, and there are several markers to determine whether a country is underdeveloped (Oduwole, 2013) and the study will seek to understand development through the lens of Seers' conception of development as a 'good change'. This perspective offers a comprehensive view of development that does not "equate growth with development" rather this approach focuses on going beyond the economic metrics by associating development with the mitigation of poverty, unemployment, and inequality (Seers, 1972) as cited in (McGillivray, 2016).

Nigeria's underdevelopment is a complex issue characterized by a range of interconnected factors that hinder its economic and social progress. These factors include dependence on a single export (crude oil), a weak industrial base, high unemployment, income inequality, and a history of corruption and poor governance (Akpomera, (2015). These issues are further compounded by a lack of diversification, inadequate infrastructure, and a poorly developed human capital base. (Seers 1972) argue that "it looks as if economic growth not merely may fail to solve social and political difficulties; certain types of growth can cause them." moreover, the term 'development' itself is synonymous with progress. Furthermore, the method that this approach determines

progress is if the following three issues are mitigated; ‘poverty’, ‘unemployment’, and ‘inequality’ (Seers, 1972).

Thus, this implies that the issue of underdevelopment can be viewed as the inverse of development since development indicates that the economy is developing or moving forward by tackling the issues stated above, hence underdevelopment is not only an indicator that represents a lack of development rather in certain areas there is a stagnation or regression in solving the economic ailments. Therefore, this perspective goes beyond simply relying on economic indicators as the metric to judge development as this study intends to do. Henceforth, the study utilizes the inverse of Seers’ formulation as another definition of underdevelopment when the country continues to suffer from the ailments of poverty, unemployment, and inequality, thereby classifying it as underdeveloped.

Development, like many terms within the social sciences, does not have a unive rsally accepted definition. Developmental definitions often reference improvements in the quality of human life. (Naomi 1995) notes that development typically entails not just economic growth but elements of fair distribution, access to health care, education, housing and other vital services, all aimed at enhancing both individual and collective quality of life. (Gboyega, 2003) perceives development as an idea encompassing all initiatives to elevate the conditions of human existence across various dimensions. It represents a transformation or progress towards a more desirable state (Chukwuemeka, Ugwuanyi & Amobi, 2013).

If development is considered in terms of improvement in the quality of human life, it therefore implies that a country can be regarded as being developed only when it is able to provide qualitative living standard for its citizens. Regrettably, Nigeria has not been able to provide such living standard for its citizens. There have been numerous policies, plans and programmes aimed at achieving development in Nigeria, but these have not brought the required change in the country. The country still remains grossly underdeveloped and largely characterized by poverty, inequality and lack of basic infrastructure. Thus, Nigeria has failed in its development efforts, as observed by (Okon and Thompson (2020).

Policy as a Concept

Policy is an intentional set of rules to direct choices and produce logical results. Implemented as a protocol or procedure, a policy is a declaration of intent. The governance body of an organization typically adopts policies (*Voican, 2008*). It is possible for policies to support both subjective and objective decision-making. Because they must be based on the relative merits of several factors, policies used in subjective decision-making typically help senior management make decisions that are difficult to test objectively. Also, policies are implemented by governments and other organizations through laws, rules, procedures, administrative actions, incentives, and voluntary practices.

In order to facilitate objective decision-making, policies are typically operational in nature and subject to objective testing (*Gade, 2023*). It has been argued that policies ought to be evidence-based. An individual or organization is justified in claiming that a specific policy is evidence-based if, and only if, three conditions are met. First, the individual or organization possesses comparative evidence about the effects of the specific policy in comparison to the effects of at least one alternative policy. Second, the specific policy is supported by this evidence according to at least one of the individual's or organization's preferences in the given policy area. Third, the individual or organization can provide a sound account for this support by explaining the evidence and preferences that lay the foundation for the claim (*Lowi, 1972*). Policies are dynamic; they are not just static lists of goals or laws. Policy blueprints have to be implemented, often with unexpected results. Social policies are what happens 'on the ground' when they are implemented, as well as what happens at the decision making or legislative stage.

Inconsistency Policy in Nigeria

Inconsistency is the quality or state of being inconsistent. To be inconsistent is to lose the sequence of one's actions. Policy inconsistency resulting from changes in policy sometimes emerges from the attempt of leaders to reform society not necessarily to create a setback for the citizenry. Where a leader has amended a policy, not for national interests or development, but to tarnish the predecessors, such policy is likely to fail. Policy

inconsistency occurs in many countries with the change of governments. For instance, in Nigeria, several economic, political and social policies have changed due to changes in governments from one political part or same political party to another. This could be the reason why Oaikhena (2021) argued that “the restriction of national planning efforts towards economic development, only with scant reference to social, political and cultural development is often times recorded in Africa”.

Nigeria faces several hindrances in achieving its economic and developmental goals. But, one of the most profound is policy inconsistency and discontinuity. The national council on development planning (NCDC) recognized the lack of stability and continuity in programmes by succeeding governments as the bane of Nigeria’s stunted growth and development. Very few policies have stood the test of time.

Most politicians are entirely focused on getting re-elected rather than enforcing feasible and viable politics that actually drive long-term growth. As a result, the frequent change of government after election often leads to a complete or partial disruption of the policies enacted by the previous administration (Whether good or bad). While it is understandable that the incoming administration might have an alternative vision and might want to gain legitimacy by introducing new policies, the intent behind their actions is not always patriotic. Governments have a sense of “my policy”. The Abuja-Kaduna railway is a typical example; where supporters of ex-president Goodluck Jonathan did not let Nigerians forget that “Jonathan began it and Buhari finished it”.

Theoretical Framework

There have been various attempts by scholars to explain why some countries are developed and others are underdeveloped. These scholars, in their attempt, often queue behind two popular paradigms of development/underdevelopment. One of such paradigms is the modernization of school. According to (Okereke and Ekpe 2002), the central thesis of the Modernization School is that, under development in Nigeria is internally generated and perpetuated due to the traditional or primitive character of the society.

Consequently, modernization theorists advocate for the adoption of western economic paradigms as key to the development of the Third World whose

underdevelopment results from internal contradictions within their territories. As explained by Igwe (2010), such internal contradictions are evident from the way and manner resources are allocated in these societies, as well as the parochial beliefs, attitudes and values of the people which together with the character of the policies of governance are incongruent to development.

Within the Modernization School, there are several theories that seek to explain development and underdevelopment among countries of the world. One of such theories is the Socio-Cultural Theory which is based on the premise that what creates the necessary conditions for economic development in any society are the changes in social, cultural and institutional orders of society. One of the socio-cultural theorists, Manning Nash cited in (Okereke and Ekpe 2002), explained that since economic development is a process of social change, it must be seen to involve three related kinds of social action, namely: i) The choice to institute changes; ii. The bringing together of the means and facilities to implement the choice; and iii) The organization of social and cultural life so that growth becomes a built-in feature of the social system.

Nash stated further that lack of capital for productive investment is among the many problems facing Third World countries. He added that his study of Burma and Cambodia has, however, shown that the social structures and cultural patterns which enhance savings and investments vary from one country to another. In line with the views of modernization theorists, (Dike 2015) argued that Nigeria lacks the critical institutions and infrastructure capable of transforming the society into the 21st century system. For (Dike 2015), the Nigerian system is colored by unbridled corruption, non-functional health care and education systems, and institutions and infrastructure that are antithetical to capacity development; and these forces have resulted in a weak economy, rising youth unemployment, and poverty as well as insecurity in the society. In their assessment, (Okon and Thompson 2020) agreed, on one hand, with modernization theorists that the underdevelopment of Third World countries is mostly internally generated and perpetuated.

According to them, there is evidence to prove that most of Nigeria's problems are internally generated and perpetuated by Nigerian political elites - who seem to be

comfortable with the country's underdevelopment situation; notwithstanding the fact that the many years of colonialism and neocolonialism have, in one way or the other, also affected the pursuit of development in Nigeria. In another breath, (Okon and Thompson 2020) frown at the attempt by modernization theorists to demote the cultures of Third World countries.

Eme (2013) argued that culture *per se* cannot stop a peasant or an investor from taking advantage of a prominent situation that can promote his welfare. They further observed that wealth and achievement are valued among the Igbos. Therefore, given the right incentive, that progressive culture of hard-work and achievement can be stimulated to achieve the goals of agrarian modernization and industrialization. In this regard, Idachaba (1975), was of the opinion that if developing countries are interested in planned change in their peasant economies, they need to identify the positive elements which promote change within their societies, while at the same time identifying those elements that can possibly impede progress.

Methodology

This paper relied on secondary sources of data. Data were gathered by the researchers through an extensive and in-depth review of relevant literatures on Nigeria's underdevelopment. The sources of the literatures were thoroughly evaluated and analyzed. Citizens dis-alignment with government policies a panacea for Nigeria underdevelopment. Data generated were used for study analysis.

Government failures and way forward

The Nigeria government has failed in its development efforts, in spite of her citizen's right to policies. According to Dike (2015), Nigeria's system is colored by unbridled corruption, non-functional health care and education systems, and institutions and infrastructure that are antithetical to capacity development. According to him, these forces have resulted in weak economy, rising youth unemployment, and poverty as well as insecurity in the society. The Nigerian economy has over the decades been characterized by galloping inflation, unequal foreign exchange rate exasperated by devalued currency

and persistent dependence on importation (Eme, 2013), and despite the country's increase in oil wealth, majority of its citizens wallow in poverty (Okon and Thompson, 2020).

As noted by the World Bank and Department for International Development (2005), nearly 70 million Nigerians live on less than \$1 per day, 54 percent of Nigerians live below the poverty line (UNDP, 2006) and over one-third live in extreme poverty (UNDP, 2006b). Nigeria's poverty rate is hovering around 43.3 percent of the estimated population of 170 million (Emejo, 2014). Dike (2015) stated that: *“Many Nigerians appear to have entrepreneurial skills; they are very creative and innovative. But the unpredictable and un-conducive, extractive political institutions and unfriendly business environment have stunted their zeal. ...It takes a lot of passion and determination to keep your business running and to market your products or services under the poor business environment in Nigeria”*.

There is also stagnation in Nigeria's educational sector. Singapore in the early 1960s had educational statistics similar to that of many African countries, including Nigeria; but as at 2019, the nation's literacy rate stood at 97 percent while Nigeria, on the other hand, was only able to improve the literacy rate to 60 percent (Rufai, 2019). The standard of education in Nigeria has been falling; teaching and learning are based on theory with little or no practical application of what the students learned in the classroom (Dike, 2015). According to Afolayan (2014), this falling standard of education in Nigeria is due to lack of proper funding and planning. In Nigeria, students are taught under un-conducive learning environments and teachers are not adequately motivated. While Secondary School (High School) graduates in educational institutions in Nigeria churned out yearly are ill-prepared to face the rigorous of university education, the age-long disagreement between the Federal Government and the Academic Staff Union of Universities (ASUU) has disrupted the academic calendar of higher institutions.

These pose serious problems for the development of creative, innovative and productive citizens (Dike, 2015). Nigeria's health care system is plague with problems. Apart from lack of cordial relationship between health care providers and patients, poorly equipped health centres and hospitals are spread all over the country (The Health Workers Strike, 2014; Dantiye, 2015) and these have prevented the health care providers from

providing quality services to Nigerians. As opined by Musawa (2014), lots of Nigerians die from preventable diseases such as high blood pressure, hypertension, prostate cancer, diabetes, breast cancer, maternal child birth issues and malnutrition due to the country's poor health care system. Consequently, the political elites and those who can afford the cost, often travel abroad to receive high quality health care services at the expense of the masses (Dantiye, 2015). Thus, ordinary citizens often rely on the assistance of private individuals in order to resolve their basic health problems (The Health Workers Strike, 2014).

As observed by Dike (2015), the medical doctors and other health care workers are often on strike to press home their demands over diverse issues, including non-payment of salaries and allowances, which often lead to unnecessary loss of lives. However, some people are of the opinion that the health care professionals in Nigeria care only about their remuneration than provision of health services to the needy (News Agency of Nigeria, 2014). Worse still, Nigerians have lost faith in the country's health care system as their perception of Nigeria's health care workers is that of uneducated, unskilled, unreliable and hardhearted care providers (Dantiye, 2015). Given the above background, Nigeria has presented itself as a country that is characterized by failed development.

Accordingly, Okon and Thompson (2020) identify Nigeria as a country which, in spite of her huge resources, has failed in its development efforts, while Rufai (2019) described the country as one that is stuck in perpetual underdevelopment because, the more things change the more they remain the same. Citizens and Failed Development in Nigeria There are differing opinions on why Nigeria, with its human and natural resources, has failed to achieve development and this debate has been on for several decades. Some have noted that Nigeria's developmental challenges are due to the capitalist world economic system. Yet others (Achebe, 1983; Dike, 2015; Rufai, 2019; Okon and Thompson, 2020) have observed that Nigeria has failed in its development efforts because of the absence of good leadership.

According to Achebe (1983), the trouble with Nigeria is simply and squarely a failure of leadership. Dike (2015) sees Nigerian political leaders as those who seem to

have a “fixed mind-set”, which has prevented them from adopting and implementing effective socio-political and economic policies to transform the society. Rather than chart a path towards national development, Nigerian leaders engage in pervasive distribution struggles which often result in political instability and the erosion of good governance (Rufai, 2019). Leadership is of utmost importance in the development of any nation - and given the caliber of leaders that have ruled Nigeria since its independence; the country seems not to be ambitious enough for development (Okon and Thompson, 2020). Although there are enough resources to achieve the much needed development in Nigeria, the looting and mismanagement of the resources by political elites have perpetually prevented the country from achieving development. As has been rightly noted by Dike (2015), the root cause of the present social, political and economic predicaments in Nigeria is not the making of leaders alone but collective selfishness.

For instance, corruption has often been identified as being a bane of Nigeria's socio-economic development, but it is not only the political elites that are responsible for the endemic corruption in the country. There is no doubt that most of Nigeria's leaders are notoriously corrupt; however, some citizens are as corrupt, if not more, as the leaders in Nigeria. In reality, the only reason why some of these Nigerians remain incorruptible is that they lack the opportunity to be corrupt. It is on record that some Nigerians give bribes in order to gain admission into higher institutions of learning or get employment in the civil service or other organizations, regardless of qualifications and merit. Amid corruption in Nigeria, vision, policy, plan, politics, principle, conscience, wealth, commerce, pleasure sports, knowledge, science, worship and morality are all corrupt (Eneh, 2011).

This means that corruption is not only in political offices; it is also present in markets, schools, churches, stadia and in the minds of most Nigerians. For Eneh (2011), patriotism is a stranger to an average Nigerian's lexicon, the federal character and Nigerian factor having replaced merits and rights. Today, anyone in Nigeria could be extremely rich and famous without any known source of income and nobody questions such wealth and fame (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012). Dike 2015 states that in Nigeria:

...Public servants do not show up for work on time and do not take their work seriously, and they expect to get paid every month without being productive.

The mentality that hard work and honesty does not pay (or is not properly rewarded) has found its way into the school system as students do not take their studies seriously any longer. The “I don't care attitude” and the mentality to get rich through fraud often discourage the spirit of competition and hard work, and thus, inhibit national development”t. In addition, it is the responsibility of the people to monitor the activities of the political leaders with a view to reviewing their mandate for good performance or using constitutional provisions to fire them for nonperformance (Eneh, 2011).

Every Nigerian is a stakeholder in the affairs of the nation (Dike, 2015). However, some Nigerians do not care about what happens in the country and have failed in ensuring that the leaders honour the social contract they entered into with the citizens. Instead of Nigerian leaders to redesign the system to make it function effectively, they engage in patching problems and the citizens allow them to continue in doing so (Dike, 2015). It is important to note that developed and progressive countries became what they are today because their people fought and overthrew the powerful political elites who dominated political power, and thus, create a society where political rights were properly shared and the government was responsive to the needs of the people (Acemoglu and Robinson, 2012). But the citizens have been unable to do so in Nigeria.

Thus, Nigerian leaders have been taking the citizens for a ride because the citizens seem to be enjoying the ride. Majority of Nigerians are traumatized and dying of extreme poverty and hunger, while a privileged few have, by fair or foul means, cornered and monopolized Nigeria's economic, political, health and sociocultural commonwealth (Eneh, 2011). This situation is disheartening, but it does not justify why some citizens develop attitudes that are inimical to development. Rather than hold the leaders accountable for mismanagement and injustice in the country, some citizens have resorted to wrong reactions. One of such reactions has been the insecurity situation in the country which has driven away potential investors, especially from the northern part of the country.

Also, issues of indiscriminate disposal of waste, open defecation, vandalism of public facilities and disobedience to law and order by citizens remain detrimental to Nigeria's development. Another wrong reaction or responses to Nigeria's ugly situation by citizens is brain drain (Eneh, 2008). Evidently, Nigeria's date with destiny has been put on hold because of the citizen's attitude towards the political system and the leadership behavior towards what they should be doing for the citizens, for overall development of the country (Anazodo, Uchenna and Uche, 2022). Therefore, some citizens are to blame for Nigeria's failed development, together with the leaders. Thus the way forward are highlighted as follows:

- a) Primarily, the solution to Nigeria's underdevelopment lies in good governance. Political elites must endeavor to fulfill their promises of bringing development to the country and must pay adequate attention to uplifting the impoverished and dehumanized Nigerian citizenry.
- b) There should be a change of the citizens' orientation. Nigerians must realize that they have a great role to play in the country's development and the need to participate in policy making, both at the input and output stages.
- c) Citizens must equally learn to hold leaders accountable for their stewardship and must be willing to co-operate with government in all its efforts toward the development of Nigeria.
- d) Government should be flexible in policy making.
- e) One of the major panacea to underdevelopment in any country is the involvement of the citizen(s) in taking drastic decision.
- f) Lastly, the burden of Nigeria' development does not fall solely at the feet of political elites; when faced with opportunities to contribute to the country's development, each Nigerian must remember to bear his/her own moral burden.

Discussion of findings

Target Beneficiaries: It can be said that no single government policy plan is sufficient to meet the needs of the people. It is good to target a specific group for a better policy implementation. The target group should be involved at the formulation stage in order for

them to contribute in what affect(s) their lives. This will also give them a sense of belonging and commitment.

Interaction and Communication between Government and the other Organizations:

Adequate attention should be given the nongovernmental organizations, professional bodies, organized private sector and the civil society groups in the policy process. These group invariably represents the larger citizens.

Monitoring of Project: There should be provision for adequate monitoring of projects, to stop the problem of abandoned projects and to ensure the realization of policy goals.

Adequate Resources: Adequate material and human resources needed to implement the policy should be provided.

Effective Communication: There must be effective communication between the target beneficiaries and the implementers of policy programs.

Encourage the Culture of Continuity: The culture of discontinuity of policies should be discouraged. The national and state assemblies should enact laws that will guarantee continuity of policies made to enhance growth and development. There should be continuity in policy, except when the policy is found not to be useful to the people.

Substantial Effort and Continuity of Efforts: Policy implementation will not automatically follow from policy decisions but needs to be treated as a positive purposive process in it. Consequently, substantial effort is required to follow policy from intention to action; and the resources needed for adequate implementation of relevant policies needs to be provided to realize policy objectives.

Conclusion

Without doubt, the fundamental cause of Nigeria's underdevelopment is poor leadership and governance which has resulted in weak economy, poor institutions, dilapidated infrastructural facilities and low quality education above all poor policy making etc. But beyond the country's bad leadership, citizens do also contribute to the underdevelopment in Nigeria. Without the citizens being patriotic to the country; without the citizens holding the leaders accountable for their stewardship; and without the citizens showing genuine interest in the country's development, Nigeria may continue to remain underdeveloped. It

seems difficult for ordinary Nigerians alone, without political power, to bring the needed change in the country; however, each time the citizens are faced with an opportunity to contribute to Nigeria's development, they should do so with sincerity and patriotism.

a) Recommendations

- b) In considering citizen participation for the objective of advancing public accountability in the policy making, a successful citizen participation programme should be well organized, constructive, systematic and legally binding to have chances of achieving positive impact (Golubovic, 2010). Well-organized citizen participation entails facilitation of information sharing between the institutions and actors involved in decision making. The information should be objective, reliable, and up to date and user friendly to those involved (OECD, 2001). For example, when dealing with local citizens who can barely read, it is inappropriate to design leaflets or pamphlets as information dissemination tool since it bars their chances of learning.
- c) In addition, there should also be clear goals and rules that govern the interactions and processes in the exercise of participation (Yang & Callahan, 2005). These goals and rules should define the bounds and exact intents of the participation exercise to ascertain a concrete potential base of accountability and transparency in the decision-making processes (Malena et al., 2004). The processes of citizen participation should be open to public scrutiny to ensure transparency (Phillips & Orsini, 2002:9). At the same-time, the results of a citizen participation process should demonstrate the strength of citizens' voice (Arnstein, 1969).
- d) However, often in democratic politics the dependent factors of citizen participation don't play out quite like this due to unlevelled interplay of power factors and policy making interest among involved actors or institutions. For example, many governments in developing countries despite being democratic are reported to have imbalances on information sharing, setting participatory structures and mechanisms of accountability (World Bank, 2004; Laurian & Shaw, 2008). 4. Most of these governments release generic information on citizen participation that is not user

friendly to the task at hand (Agrawal & Ribot, 1999). They also don't set supporting legal sanctions of ensuring public accountability in order to still maintain control of things over the citizens, and also avert local accountability (Agrawal & Ribot, 1999). Also, due to limited time of office, many democratic governments are interested in achieving substantive policy objectives which overrides citizen participation in achieving the substantive policies. Hence, this paper supports a continuum approach to analyzing citizen participation.

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